

A Graphene-Based Electrochemical Platform for Alzheimer's Disease Prognosis

Ronaldo Challhua¹, Marianna Rossetti¹, Ruslan Alvarez-Diduk¹, Arben Merkoçi^{1,2}

¹ *Nanobioelectronics and Biosensors Group, Catalan Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (ICN2), CSIC and BIST, Campus UAB, Bellaterra, 08193 Barcelona, Spain.* ² *Catalan Institution for Research and Advanced Studies (ICREA) Passeig de Lluís Companys, 23, Barcelona, 08010, Spain.*

Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is the most common form of dementia [1]. Its prognosis currently relies on diagnostic methods that are expensive, invasive, or time-consuming. These methods, based on blood biomarkers, still face challenges, and the design of cost-effective and simple testing protocols remains a significant barrier.

Here, we propose a novel and cost-effective Point-of-Care (PoC) system for early diagnosis of AD and progression. Leveraging a low-cost green IR laser-assisted print/stamp technology, we fabricate reduced graphene oxide (rGO) electrodes that can be integrated into lateral flow assay (LFA) strips [3]. These rGO electrodes can be functionalized with aptamers that specifically bind to key AD biomarkers, e.g. Glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), enabling their accurate and sensitive detection. Our platform holds great promise for decentralized, rapid, and affordable monitoring of Alzheimer's-related biomarkers, paving the way for improved disease prognosis and personalized care.

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References

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